

RDM checklist

Start with...

RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT

- Read your institute's RDM policy
- Write a Data Management Plan

ETHICS

Contact the ethics committee for

- ethical approval (if required)
- Informed consent templates

PRIVACY

- Do a pre-DPIA (Data Protection Impact Assessment) when working with personal data

Continue with...

- Store research data in a facility that is adequate in terms of availability, integrity and confidentiality

End with...

Archive and/or publish your research data:

- In a trustworthy repository
- With clear documentation and metadata
- As open as possible, as closed as necessary
- Findable and Accessible (FAIR)
- For at least 10 years
- As pseudonymised or anonymised as possible
- With an access level and licence or Data Use Agreement that suit the level of sensitivity of the data